

SANSA ACTIVITIES

- WORLD SPIDER CATALOG (WSC)

Presently, 2 265 spider species are listed on the South African National Species List. These are species that have been described from South Africa, as well as those identified during SANSA surveys in South Africa. These are usually species described from other countries but also recorded in South Africa and 225 South African species are not yet listed in the WSC. One of the aims of SANSA is to get all these species recognised and listed on the WSC. For a species to be listed, enough distribution data and detail on the morphology and genitalia need to be provided before it is recognised.

Over the last three years, we were able to add 43 species to the WSC through articles published in the SANSA Newsletter, as well as through the Spider Identification Guides so far listed on the WSC.

Presently the WSC reached a total number of 50 000 species. Therefore the species recorded from South Africa represent 4.5% of the total.

- SANSANENODO REPOSITORY

SANSA now uses Zenodo as a general-purpose repository to deposit research-related digital artefacts. SANSA has registered and set up a community within Zenodo to archive data and output over the 25-year history of SANSA.

Anyone can access the SANSA community on Zenodo following this link <https://zenodo.org/communities/sansa/> and search for content within this community. We have already loaded >58 SANSA articles on Zenodo. These include the latest SANSA newsletters and SANSA articles, as well as 31 of the Spider Identification Guides. Migration of SANSA data continues. There seems to be an interest in the SANSA activities and the documents are viewed and downloaded.

- SPIDER IDENTIFICATION GUIDES

There are still about 14 spider families for which Spider Identification Guides need to be completed. As new taxonomic data become available, the guides need to be upgraded and new versions (e.g. Araneidae, Hahniidae and Drymusidae) can be downloaded from Zenodo.

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SANSA BOOKS

The following books produced as part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) are still available from the Agricultural Research Council. The books were a joint effort of the Agricultural Research Council, University of the Free State and University of Venda and sponsorships came from E. Oppenheimer & Son. For more information please contact Hendrieta Moletsane, e-mail: MoletsaneH@arc.agric.za; Tel: 012 808 8000/8108 or Tel: 012 808 8000/8108, or Booksales@arc.agric.za.

Spiders of the Kalahari

AUTHORS: Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman & Almie van den Berg

Plant Protection Research Institute Handbook no 18, Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria. 120 pp. ISBN 978-1-86849-382-1.

This book was the first attempt to provide information on the spiders of a specific area – the Kalahari. The area covered by Kalahari sands extends over 2.5 million km² of the interior of central Southern Africa. These wind-blown sands are the largest continuous stretch of sand in the world. It is regarded as one of Africa’s last wilderness areas where minimal human impact has contributed to its preservation. Presently, 243 species from 41 families are known from the region. Desert spiders have developed their own means of coping with the high temperatures, long hours of sunlight, long periods without rain and water and the large amounts of salt present in this unique environment.

PRICE : R250.00

Spiders of the Savanna Biome

AUTHORS: Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman, Stefan Foord & Charles Haddad

University of Venda & Agricultural Research Council 2013: 134 pp. ISBN: 978-1-86849-421-7

This book is the first to provide information on the 62 spider families, 381 genera and 1 230 species found in the Savanna Biome of South Africa. A total of 23 739 records from 1 260 localities have so far been recorded from the Savanna Biome; of these, 308 are endemic to the biome. The purpose of this book is primarily to provide baseline information on spider diversity in an area that has previously been poorly sampled.

PRICE : R300.00

Spiders of the Grassland Biome

AUTHORS: Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman & Charles Haddad

Plant Protection Research Institute Handbook No. 19, Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria 2014: 120 pp. ISBN: 13-978-1-86849-429-3

This book is the first to provide information on the 58 families, 275 genera and 792 species of spiders found in the Grassland Biome of South Africa. Of these, 58 species are endemic to the biome. The purpose of this book is primarily to provide baseline information on diversity in an area that has previously been poorly sampled. Descriptive characters for the families, genera and species are provided, with information on their guilds and behaviour. The book is richly illustrated with >600 colour photographs. The focus of this book is on the families and genera that are likely to be encountered, as many spider species are small and often not easily seen.

PRICE : R250.00

ANOTHER NEW BOOK ON SA SPIDERS SOON!!

SPIDERS OF THE FERNKLOOF NATURE RESERVE AND SURROUNDING FYNBOS

Little is so far known about the spider fauna of the Fernkloof Nature Reserve (FNR) and the surrounding fynbos. Fynbos is one of the most diverse yet distinctive floras in the world, and is characterised by unique treeless evergreen heathlands and shrublands growing on nutrient-poor soil, and is dominated by small, leathery-leafed and evergreen grass-like shrubs and dependent on periodic veld fires. Fynbos is a subdivision of the Cape Floral Kingdom (CFK), the smallest of the six Global Floral Kingdoms. The FNR covers 1 800 ha in the Kleinrivier Mountains above Hermanus in the Western Cape province.

This reserve is a fine example of fynbos, with six of the seven endemic plant families with over 1 600 species of the CFK representing an extremely high plant and possibly spider species diversity. The aim of this book is to provide information on the spider diversity of the reserve and surrounding fynbos.

Surveys so far showed that the FNR is home to a rich spider fauna represented by 45 families, 139 genera and 206 species. The most species-rich families are:

- Thomisidae (21 spp.)
- Salticidae (19 spp.)
- Araneidae (19 spp.)
- Lycosidae (15 spp.)
- Theridiidae (14 spp.)

Thirty-three species known from the reserve are Western Cape endemic species and ten species are of special concern.

Victor Hamilton-Attwell is presently busy with a survey of the FNR with a team of very enthusiastic helpers (Hamilton-Attwell, 2018a & 2018b; Hamilton-Attwell & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2020). He has received funding from the Hermanus Botanical Society to produce this book on spiders. This will be undertaken in collaboration with Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman.

Fernkloof Nature Reserve. (Photo: V. Hamilton-Attwell)

Some Fernkloof Nature Reserve spiders. (Photos: Jan Bosselaers)

REFERENCES

HAMILTON-ATTWELL V.L. 2018a. Visitor to Fernkloof Nature Reserve. *SANSA Newsletter* 31: 3.

HAMILTON-ATTWELL V.L. 2018b. Spiders from Fernkloof Nature Reserve. *SANSA Newsletter* 31: 4.

HAMILTON-ATTWELL V.L. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2020. Observations on the egg-sacs of four *Palystes* spp. in the Fernkloof Nature Reserve (Araneae: Sparassidae. *SANSA Newsletter* 35(2020): 1–4.

If you have any photographs of spiders from that area that you would like to share, please contact Victor at vicattwell@sonicmail.co.za.

NEW RESEARCH

MORE ON THE DIET OF PALPIMANIDAE

PEKÁR S., DUŠÁTKOVÁ L.P., MACHÁČKOVÁ T., SLABÝ O., GARCÍA L.F. & HADDAD C.R. 2022. Gut-content analysis in four species, combined with comparative analysis of trophic traits, suggests an araneophagous habit for the entire family Palpimanidae (Araneae). *Organisms Diversity & Evolution* 22: 265–274.

Spiders are one of the most diverse and abundant predator groups in terrestrial ecosystems around the world, but little is known about the diet of the majority of species. There are limited data particularly for families that have been suggested to be dietary specialists, such as palpimanid spiders. In this study, the trophic strategy of four palpimanid species (*Diaphorocellus biplagiatus*, *Otiotrops birabeni*, *Palpimanus gibbulus* and *P. potteri*) representing all three subfamilies (Chediminae, Otiotropsinae, Palpimaninae) and three biogeographical areas (Mediterranean, South America, South Africa) were investigated in order to infer a trophic strategy for the entire family Palpimanidae.

Palpimanidae is a small family represented by 18 genera and 154 species, but the group is in desperate need of modern revision. Palpimanids are often rare to collect and to observe in nature, which not only hampers research on their taxonomy, as many species have only recently been described or redescribed, but also on their ecology. In fact, their life history remains enigmatic and much of the information that is available is anecdotal.

We predicted that all palpimanids are specialised araneophagous predators. Using molecular gut-content analysis, combined with comparative analysis of morphological trophic traits, we found all four species to catch other spiders more often than insects. All species captured spiders belonging to several families, but predominantly those of the cursorial guild. The diet composition did not differ between sexes and juveniles. The breadth of the trophic niche was narrow for all species, suggesting stenophagy. Using comparative analysis of morphological traits (thick cuticle, stout forelegs, scopulae on forelegs, and stridulatory apparatus) and araneophagy, we estimated that preying on spiders, combined with the morphological traits, is an ancestral state for the entire family. It was therefore suggested that the whole family Palpimanidae includes araneophagous species.

Diaphorocellus biplagiatus were collected by hand at Bankfontein farm in the western Free State (Figs 1 & 2). In *Diaphorocellus*, most specimens captured other spiders, but also insects such as ants, termites, cockroaches, flies, springtails, and grasshoppers. Among spiders, at least eight families were represented, with sequences mainly from Gnaphosidae, Zodariidae and Salticidae, so that 84.6% of spider prey belong to the cursorial guild. These spider families are regularly encountered under rocks, where *Diaphorocellus* is often found.

Palpimanus potteri were collected at Ndumo Game Reserve in northern KwaZulu-Natal. Prey availability was determined in the microhabitat that they were sampled in, namely the bark of *Vachellia xanthophloea* (Fig. 3), where they construct retreats under loose bark (Haddad, 2016). In this microhabitat, the spider fauna is dominated by cursorial Trachelidae and Salticidae, and web-building Theridiidae, which were the dominant components of *P. potteri*'s diet. Cheiracanthiidae were less common, but still extensively fed on. One common denominator is that all these spider families build resting retreats or capture webs under bark, likely making them susceptible to successful attack by *P. potteri*.

REFERENCE

HADDAD C.R. 2016. Diversity and ecology of spider assemblages associated with *Vachellia xanthophloea* bark in a South African reserve (Arachnida: Araneae). *African Entomology* 24: 321–333.

Fig. 1. *Diaphorocellus biplagiatus* (Photo: Charles Haddad)

Fig. 2. A shale-dominated karoo habitat on Bankfontein farm, where *Diaphorocellus biplagiatus* was sampled (Photo: Charles Haddad)

Fig. 3. *Vachellia xanthophloea* trees at Ndumo Game Reserve where *Palpimanus potteri* was sampled (Photo: Charles Haddad)

TALK PRESENTED AT THE SOUTHERN AFRICAN MOUNTAIN CONFERENCE (SEE P. 6)

SPIDERS ACROSS THE SOUTPANSBERG

Stefan Foord, Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman & Caswell Munyai

Diversity patterns along elevations are influenced by both contemporary and historical processes. Identifying the relative role of these processes provides insight into their response to global change drivers and aid the interpretation of monitoring results.

The Soutpansberg is an ancient inselberg in Southern Africa influenced by a diverse range of biogeographical elements and contemporary drivers of change. Here we report on patterns of spider diversity across the two dominant aspects of the mountain (north and south) over a nine-year period. We describe spider diversity patterns, richness and species composition over time and across the mountain and identify species associated with the different habitats found on the mountain.

Students of the University of Venda sampling in the Soutpansberg.

The figure below is an ordination of the spider assemblages and suggests that there are considerable overlaps between spiders of the northern and southern aspects. Much of the variation is linked to the vegetation structure associated with each of the habitats.

Different sites sampled in the Soutpansberg.

Spiders were sampled twice a year during the hot-dry and hot-wet seasons, in 11 elevational zones that were spaced at 200 m altitudinal distances. Sampling within a zone consisted of four replicates that were at least 300 m apart. Replicates contained ten pitfall traps in a 10 x 50 grid. Traps were left open for five days.

Different habitat types sampled in the Soutpansberg.

The Soutpansberg is quartzitic with basalt intrusions on the south; soils are therefore more than 90% sand on the northern aspects and around summits. Transects represent a gradient from open grassy habitats through to closed forests – woody cover varies greatly across this transect from 0% to 100% and is dominated by tropical grassy biomes, which include grassland, savannah and thickets.

Climate interacts with soil to generate open woodlands on the north and grasslands on the summit. Soil fertility also varies across the mountain and influences woody vegetation structure; e.g., compacted to the open woodlands on deep sandy soils of the northern aspect, while clay content increases on the lower elevations of the southern aspect and groundwater-fed forests on the mid-elevational slopes of the southern aspect, and thicket and shrubland on the lower slopes and plains in the south.

Repeated surveying allowed us to identify species that persist through time. In the image below, the y-axis represents the number of species at an elevational zone across the x-axis, while the coloured areas represent the number of species within each of the four classes: yellow being the number of species that were present in more than half of the 12 surveys; green and yellow are those that were in more than three surveys up until the dark-blue area, which represents species that were only recorded once. From this it is clear that when considering the species that persist along the transect, richness increases with elevation and decreases at mid-elevations, while there is almost no pattern evident when considering all the species, except for peaks evident at certain elevations, particularly at 1 400 m on the northern aspect.

The Soutpansberg represents an old and climatically stable geographic feature in the region, which provides refuge for 13 endemic spider species. Contemporary processes are largely driven by habitat structure, which was the major driver of spider diversity.

RECENT PUBLICATIONS

AZEVEDO G.H.F, BOUGIE T., CARBONI M., HEDIN M. & RAMÍREZ M.J. 2022. Combining genomic, phenotypic and sanger sequencing data to elucidate the phylogeny of the two-clawed spiders (Dionycha). *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* 166: 107327. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ympev.2021.107327>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DER WALT V. & WEBB, P. 2022. New locality records for the white spotted crab spider *Firmicus bragantinus* (Brito Capello, 1866) from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 40: 10–12.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S, BOOYSEN R. & STEENKAMP R. 2022. New information on the crowned crab spider *Parasmodix quadrituberculata* Jézéquel, 1966 from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 40: 13–14.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. JONES, A. & HADDAD C.R. 2022. Notes on the silver vlei spider *Leucauge festiva* (Blackwall, 1866) from South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 40: 15–18.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & JONES A. 2022. More on the garden orb-web spider *Argiope australis* (Walckenaer, 1805) in South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae) *SANSA Newsletter* 40: 19–22.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & WIESE, L. 2022. SANSA Eastern Cape surveys: A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of Thyspunt, South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 40: 23–29.

PEKÁR S., DUŠÁTKOVÁ, L.P., MACHÁČKOVÁ, T., SLABÝ, O. & LUIS F. GARCÍA, L.F. & HADDAD C.R. 2022. Gut-content analysis in four species, combined with comparative analysis of trophic traits, suggests an araneophagous habit for the entire family Palpimanidae (Araneae). *Organisms Diversity & Evolution* 22: 265–274.

CONFERENCES

FOORD S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & MUNYAI C.T. 2022. Relative role of contemporary and historical processes in structuring spider assemblages on an isolated inselberg in southern Africa. Southern African Mountain Conference, 14–17 March 2022, Champagne Sports Resort in the central Maloti-Drakensberg, South Africa. (TALK)

FOX-CROFT, L., NOVOA, A., FOORD, S., THWALA, T., MUNYAI, C. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A. 2022. The impacts of *Parthenium hysterophorus* on ants, spiders and soil characteristics in Kruger National Park. Savanna Science Networking Meeting 6-10 March 2022, Nombolo Mdhululi Conference Centre, Skukuza Rest Camp. (TALK)

SOME FIELD OBSERVATIONS

Some more on *Trichonephila* egg sac. Photo from Allen Jones showing the egg sac of *T. fenestrata*. It seems to be a good *Trichonephila* year with large numbers reported from the Free State and Gauteng.

CRAB SPIDER FROM ONRUS

Renata Kruyswijk found this small black spider crawling out of a shell at Onrus. With the help of Vida van der Walt we were able to obtain these photographs of the male *Pactactes trimaculatus*.

Notes on the red beetle jumping spider *Pachyballus castaneus* Simon, 1900 in South Africa (Araneae: Salticidae)

Vida van der Walt¹, Bruce Blake², Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman³ & Peter Webb⁴

¹SANSa team member Gauteng (vidavdw@live.com) ⁴(† deceased); ²SANSa team member KwaZulu-Natal (mwbb@iafrica.com); ³University of Venda (DippenaarAnsie@gmail.com).

ABSTRACT: Information on the rare red beetle jumping spider *Pachyballus castaneus* Simon, 1900 is provided. As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), the species was recollected and photographed. The general morphology, behaviour, conservation status and distribution of the species are discussed along with images of live specimens.

Keywords: biodiversity, conservation, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt Biome, KwaZulu-Natal, mimicry, South African National Survey of Arachnida.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Pachyballus* Simon, 1900 is known from nine species, of which eight are recorded from Africa and one from New Caledonia (World Spider Catalog, 2022). Some species of these small spiders possibly mimic beetles.

Pachyballus castaneus Simon, 1900 was originally described from a single female housed in the National Museum of Natural History in Paris, France. The type locality was only given as Natal (South Africa). In a revision of *Pachyballus* by Wesolowska *et al.* (2020), they were unable to locate the type and they designated a neotype from the Ophathe Game Reserve, KwaZulu-Natal, to stabilise the nomenclature. They redescribed the female and described the male as the original species description was lacking detail.

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), the species was recollected and photographed. Notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa and conservation status are provided.

METHODS

During SANSa surveys, specimens were sampled from different areas in the country (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). Voucher specimens of the species are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council in Pretoria and the National Museum in Bloemfontein.

TAXONOMY

Pachyballus castaneus Simon, 1900

Pachyballus castaneus Simon, 1900: 400 (female); Wesolowska, Azarkina & Wiśniewski, 2020: 55: 6, 18–28, 129 (male, female).

Diagnostic characteristics: Small (2.5–3.00 mm length), robust spiders, with strongly flattened bodies covered with a very hard, sclerotised exoskeleton (Fig. 1); dorsum of their body has a characteristic pitted micro sculpture with short scattered pale setae (Fig. 2). Carapace reddish brown to dark brown in male (Fig. 3); eye field covers more or less half of carapace, vicinity of eyes black; white setae present around eye region (Fig. 1); posterior edge of carapace covered by abdomen. Abdomen dark reddish brown, rounded to heart shaped, as wide as long; dorsum totally covered with strongly sclerotised scutum (Figs 4–5); venter with two scuta (Fig. 7). Legs short with first pair larger than others (Figs 2–3) with femora thickened and the tibiae ventrally with dense setae. Juveniles resemble adults but more reddish (Fig. 6). Epigyne is horseshoe shaped (Figs 7–9) and palp with short embolus (Fig. 10).

Figs 1–3. *Pachyballus castaneus*: 1. Female anterior view (Photo: Vida van der Walt). 2. Female lateral view (Photo: Bruce Blake). 3. Male anterior view (Photo: Bruce Blake).

Figs 4–6. *Pachyballus castaneus*: 4. Female anterior view. 5. Female dorsal view. 6. Juvenile. (Photos: Vida van der Walt)

Figs 7–10. *Pachyballus castaneus*: 7. Female ventral view. 8. Epigyne (Photos: Vida van der Walt). 9–10. Epigyne and palp after Wesolowska *et al.* (2020).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

South Africa, Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

SOUTH AFRICA: KwaZulu-Natal: Ulundi, Ophathe Game Reserve (28°23'S, 31°24'E), (NCA 2008/4147; NCA 2008/4140; NCA 2008/4167; NCA 2008/4154; NCA 2008/3993; NCA 2008/3971); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Crocodile Centre (28°21'S, 32°25'E), (NCA 2012/5736); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, St. Lucia (28°23'S, 32°25'E), (NCA 2012/4019; NCA 2012/5737); iSimangaliso Wetland Park Lake St. Lucia, Fannies Island (28°06'S, 32°27'E), (NMBA 08069); uMkuze, Banghoek Lodge (27°45'S, 32°08'E), (NCA 2012/3965); Ndumo Game Reserve (26°55'S, 32°19'E), (NCA 2009/3660); Si-hangwane, Tembe Elephant Park, 40 km from Kosi Bay (27°02'S, 32°25'E), (NCA 94/828; NCA 2008/505); Hellsgate (28°00'S, 32°48'E), (NCA 2010/155; NCA 2010/156); Kloof (-29° 46'S, 30° 49' E) (photographs); Umhlanga (-29.737'S, 31°4'25.1"E) (photographs).
Mpumalanga: Mbombela, Agricultural College (25°27'S, 30°59'E), (NCA 2000/223); Wildlife College, 10 km from Orpen Gate of Kruger National Park (24°28'S, 31°23'E), (NCA 2003/626).
Limpopo: Little Leigh (22°56'S, 29°22'E), (NCA 2009/2232).

HABITAT

The species was sampled by beating and fogging vegetation in the Savannah (Foord *et al.*, 2011) and Indian Ocean Coastal Belt Biomes. They were sampled while beating overgrazed savannah and dense bush thicket at Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2015) and vegetation in *Vachellia xanthophloea* forests at Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006). At several localities in the iSimangaliso Wetland Park, they were mainly collected during canopy fogging of *Breonadia salicina*, *Trichilia dregeana*, *V. karroo* and *Euclea divinorum*. The Mbombela specimen was collected while beating citrus trees (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

BEHAVIOUR

The second author regularly found this species in his garden at Kloof. They usually wandered around on broadleaved plants during the daytime. Two very similar, small beetle spp. (Figs 13–14) (family Coccinellidae, possibly *Exochomus* sp.) were present on the same plants the *Pachyballus* were found. The morphological similarities between the mimic and its potential models lie in the presence of white setae covering the spider's body (Fig. 11), together with a series of tufts of long, erect, white setae on the carapace, abdomen and legs.

Figs 11–12. Coccinellidae (possibly *Exochomus* sp.). (Photos: Bruce Blake). 13–14. *Pachyballus castaneus* showing resemblance to the Coccinellidae. (Photos: Peter Webb).

They fed on a variety of insects and preyed on both nymphs and adults of booklice/barklice (order Psocoptera), jumping plant lice (family Psyllidae) and midges (family Chironomidae) (Figs 15–17). In captivity, they had a voracious appetite and readily fed on small *Drosophila melanogaster* flies. Walking was their primary means of locomotion and they only jumped when necessary to cross a void and ran very fast when they were disturbed.

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Figs 15–17. *Pachyballus castaneus* feeding on book lice (Order: Psocoptera), jumping plant lice (family Psyllidae) and Diptera midges (family: Chironomidae). (Photos: Bruce Blake)

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Notes on the red-spot hairy field spider *Neoscona triangula* (Keyserling, 1864) in South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

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ABSTRACT: The red-spot hairy field spider *Neoscona triangula* (Keyserling, 1864) described as *Epeira triangula* from Mauritius is known throughout Africa. The species is commonly found in South Africa and its general morphology, web-building behaviour and distribution are discussed along with images of live specimens.

Keywords: biodiversity, distribution, Free State, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), web-building.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Neoscona* Simon, 1864 is a large genus known from 126 species and has a wide geographical distribution. As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), a large number of specimens from several localities in South Africa were collected, many of which are members of the orb-web family Araneidae and the genus *Neoscona* (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021). One of the species, with a distinct red marking ventrally on the abdomen, was regularly sampled and photographed at night during SANSa surveys. It was identified as the red-spot hairy field spiders *Neoscona triangula* (Keyserling, 1864). The species was originally described as *Epeira triangula* from Mauritius and it has since been recorded throughout Africa (Grasshoff, 1986; World Spider Catalog, 2022).

The species is commonly found in South Africa and its general morphology, web-building behaviour and distribution are discussed and illustrated along with photographs of live specimens.

METHODS

Photographs of the species in the SANSa Virtual Museum database (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012) provided information on its morphology and behaviour. Voucher specimens are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria (NCA).

Observations on web-building behaviour was undertaken at Mpetsane Conservation Estate (MCE) in the Free State province. Most of the photographs were taken and observations made by the first author (AJ) while staying on the estate.

MORPHOLOGY

Diagnostic characteristics: Size: total length females 9–17 mm, males 7–9 mm. Carapace mottled, varies from creamish-brown to dark grey (Figs 1 & 3); densely covered with white setae; longitudinal thoracic fovea. Abdomen broad, rounded, longer than wide; mottled; clothed with fine setae with scattered longer setae in between; dorsum with both longitudinal and transverse blackish brown bands (Figs 3 & 8). Ventrally species is recognised by a red marking that varies in shape between specimens (Figs 2 & 4). Legs dorsally faintly banded; ventrally dark; with scattered setae. Female epigyne gradually narrowing towards the long scape (Figs 3–4). Male smaller than female; tibiae I and II with strong setae (Fig. 7); abdomen more oval than in female; with short dark transverse bands (Fig. 8).

Figs 1–4. *Neoscona triangula* female: 1 & 3. Dorsal views. 2 & 4. Ventral views. (Photos: 1. Peter Webb, 2. Les Oates, 3–4. Stefan Nesper)

Figs 5–9. *Neoscona triangula*: 5. Epigyne (after Grasshoff, 1986). 6. Epigyne. 7. Setae on tibiae I and II of male (after Grasshoff, 1986). 8. Male abdomen. 9. Female abdomen (8–9 after Grasshoff, 1986).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Neoscona triangula distribution in Africa (after Grasshoff, 1986).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Eastern Cape: Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Coega (-33.76, 25.65); East London (-33.01, 27.90); Grahamstown (-33.30, 26.52); Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Kasouga (-33.63, 26.43); Kwandwe Private Game Reserve (-33.09, 26.57); Middelburg (-31.49, 24.99); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61). **Free State:** Bethlehem (-28.23, 28.30); Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Clocolan, Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.80, 27.65); Deneysville (-26.87, 28.09); Ficksburg (-28.86, 27.86); Oranjeville (-26.99, 28.20); Philipopolis (-30.25, 25.27); Tussen-die-Riviere Nature Reserve (-30.47, 25.19); Welkom (-27.97, 26.74). **Gauteng:** Benoni (-26.19, 28.31); Brakpan (-26.23, 28.37); Bronkhorstspuit, Farm Onverwacht (-25.80, 28.74); Dunnottar (-26.35, 28.47); Irene, Gem Village Field (25.85, 28.16); Johannesburg (-26.20, 28.04); Kempton Park (-26.09, 28.23); Maraisburg (-26.11, 27.56); Midrand (-25.95, 28.14); Onderstepoort (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria/Tshwane, Rietondale Research Station (-25.73, 28.23); Randburg (-26.07, 27.92); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Roodepoort (-26.14, 27.86); Witwatersrand Botanical Gardens (-26.20, 28.04). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ashburton (-29.60, 30.38); Botha Hill (-29.48, 30.50); Dukuduku Forest Station (-28.37, 32.23); Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Giant's Cup Wilderness Reserve (-29.97, 29.46); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Lake Sibaya (-27.35, 32.70); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Mkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25);

iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.40, 32.76); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Pongola, Farm Vergeval (-27.35, 31.61); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47).

Limpopo: Bela-Bela, Highland Estate (-24.83, 28.17); Dendron, Farm Amsterdam (-23.37, 29.32); Hoedspruit (-24.34, 30.93); Luvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Leggalameetse Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Pietersburg/Polokwane (-23.89, 29.46); Springbok Flats, Tuinplaas (-24.56, 28.46). **Mpumalanga:** Brondal (-25.35, 30.84); Ermelo (-26.51, 29.98); Komatipoort, Farm Sommerreg (-25.53, 31.82); Kriel (-26.25, 29.26); Lowveld National Botanical Gardens (-25.47, 31.00); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96). **North West:** Barberspan (-26.62, 25.58); Brits (-25.62, 27.77); Hartbeespoortdam (-25.73, 27.85); Rustenburg Nature Reserve (-25.65, 27.22). **Northern Cape:** Kameeldrift (-29.38, 23.80); Kleinsee (-29.67, 17.07). **Western Cape:** Bellville (-33.90, 18.63); Caledon (-34.24, 19.43); Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); Fish Hoek, Peer Hill (-34.05, 18.35); Hermanus (-34.40, 19.25); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Knysna (-34.03, 23.00); Mur-raysburg (-31.96, 23.75); Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.35, 21.67); Table Mountain National Park (-33.82, 18.48); Tsitsikamma National Park (-33.98, 23.52); Worcester (-33.64, 19.47).

HABITAT

During SANSa surveys, the species was sampled from the Forest, Grassland, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Nama Karoo, Savanna and Thicket Biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011; Haddad *et al.*, 2013). The species was also sampled from crops such as avocado, macadamia and pecan orchards, and onion, sorghum and tomato fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

BEHAVIOUR

They construct large orb-webs at night in vegetation. They remove the web early in the morning and rest during the day on plants nearby (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2009). In South Africa, they are very commonly seen in gardens during the summer months.

Figs 10–11. *Neoscona triangula* female in a large orb-web. (Photos: Allen Jones)

WEB BUILDING

The following observations were made at Mpetsane by the first author (AJ) and a series of photographs were taken. The female was observed first on 2 January 2022 resting on a curly dock (*Rumex crispus*) plant stalk.

Each evening at approximately 8 pm the female climbed to the top of the stalk, and from the high point she turned and then produced a long (1.2–1.4 m) single silk thread that drifted outwards and downwards until it settled on a nearby plant leaf or stem. She then climbed along it until she reached the middle, where she then dropped vertically to lower-level plant leaves to anchor the thread. She repeated this exercise several times, anchoring the “main line” to nearby foliage. She then climbed halfway up, approximately 200 mm below the main line. From this point, she began to create some 17–20 parallel radial threads until she had created an orb-web some 400 mm in diameter. The web was secured by the anchor lines attached to the foliage. This all happened within 15 to 20 minutes. She then lay down the sticky spirals (Figs 10–11). She produced some 30 m of silk to create her masterpiece.

She remained in the web until just before dawn (6 am) when she began to gather the silk webbing together. She started at the central hub and worked her way around the radials, rolling the silk into a bundle (almost as large as herself). She then gathers the anchor lines, sometimes leaving the “main anchor line” in place. When she had collected all the silk, she carefully climbs down the stalk, pausing to fix the silk bundle to the vegetation (Figs 12–13). She continues downwards until she reaches the base on the stalk. She then remains hidden during the day until dusk.

Figs 12–13. *Neoscona triangula* female gathering the silk webbing and transporting it to the plant below. (Photos: Allen Jones)

The next day at sunset she became active but this time she carried her silk bundle with her. She repeated the exercise of web-building but it seems that she unwound strands from the bundle and used some of them to produce her fairly symmetrical vertical orb-web with a diameter of 400 to 450 mm. She repeated this exercise nightly for several nights, then reverted to producing new silk to make a fresh web. During a period of heavy rain and strong wind at night she stopped working until it was over, then resumed web building, often losing several hours of potential prey catching.

Some interesting adaptations to web building were made by the female. On several occasions she produced a web of which only half of the orb was symmetrical, having the regular radii (7–10), while the other half consisted of irregular silk threads (Figs 14–15). This “half-web” was often left in place at dawn and not removed.

Figs 14–15. *Neoscona triangula* female in a half orb-web. (Photos: Allen Jones)

After 23 days, the female left this site and produced a 5.35-m-long thread 1.5 m above the ground on a nearby tree. From there she then travelled to an apricot tree and in tandem with other *N. triangula* already resident there. She continued making large, full orb-webs. There were several *N. triangula* in the vicinity and they also occasionally made half orb-webs. These spiders seem to prey mainly on moths at night (Figs 16–17).

Figs 16–17. *Neoscona triangula* female in her web feeding on a moth. (Photos: Johan van Zyl)

CONSERVATION

The species has a wide distribution throughout Africa, and in South Africa it occurs in >20 protected areas such as the Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1999); Roodeplaat Dam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1989); Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006); Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2005) and Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020) and there are no significant threats to the species.

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Observations on the pale ground spiders of *Eleleis limpopo* (Araneae: Prodidomidae)

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ABSTRACT: The pale ground spiders of the genus *Eleleis* Simon, 1893 are known from nine species endemic to Africa. They are shy and small ground-dwelling spiders and very little is known about their behaviour. One of the species, *Eleleis limpopo* Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020, was sampled from several localities in South Africa. The general morphology of live specimens is discussed, with notes on their behaviour, distribution and conservation status.

Keywords: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa)

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Eleleis* Simon, 1893, represented by nine species, is known from Botswana, Cape Verde, Namibia, South Africa and Zambia (World Spider Catalog, 2022). Prior to the revision of Rodrigues and Rheims (2020), *Eleleis* was only known from the type species *Eleleis crinita* Simon, 1893. In their revision, they recognised eight new *Eleleis* species, of which four are known from South Africa.

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), spiders were sampled throughout the country Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). During the SANSa Gauteng surveys, the second author (PW) regularly sampled one of these small spiders that are now identified as *Eleleis limpopo*.

The general morphology of live specimens is discussed, with notes on their behaviour, distribution and conservation status.

METHODS

Voucher specimens sampled during SANSa surveys are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council (ARC) in Pretoria. A series of photographs were taken by PW from several localities in Gauteng.

TAXONOMIC NOTES

Eleleis belongs to the Prodidominae and this subfamily was transferred from Prodidomidae to Gnaphosidae by Azevedo *et al.* (2018); however, in a new paper, Azevedo *et al.* (2022) again recognised the family rank Prodidomidae. Species of *Eleleis* are distinguished from other Prodidomidae genera by the presence of different sized clavate setae over the entire body, except the chelicerae and spinnerets.

Eleleis limpopo Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020

Eleleis limpopo Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020: 19–27.

Diagnostic characteristics: Size TL 1.72–3.90 mm. Carapace bears a few long and oblique clavate setae (Figs 1 & 3); posterior eye row is strongly procurved and anterior eye row approximately straight; posterior median eyes and posterior lateral eyes irregular; anterior median eyes dark (Figs 2 & 8). Sternum heart shaped (Fig. 7). Abdomen ovoid, with posterior region bearing large and robust clavate setae (Figs 2 & 6); six spinnerets with anterior lateral spinnerets longer than wide (Fig. 9). Legs with clavate setae resembling spines (Figs 3 & 5); leg I strong with femora strong (Fig. 6). Male resembles the female. *E. limpopo* differs from other species of the genus by the strong brown coloration of the carapace and legs (Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020).

Figs 1–3. *Eleleis limpopo*: 1. Female from Irene. 2. Male from Groenkloof Nature Reserve. 3. Female from Irene grassland. (Photos: Peter Webb)

Figs 4–7. *Eleleis Limpopo*: 4. Female habitus dorsal view. 5. Male habitus dorsal view. 6. Female dorsal view (alcohol material). 7. Female ventral view (alcohol material). (Photos: 4–5 Peter Webb. 6–7 Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman)

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

South Africa, Gambia.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

SOUTH AFRICA. Gauteng: Irene Gem Village Field (-25.89, 28.23), (NCA 2014/2209); Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.8, 28.74); Groenkloof Nature Reserve (-25.78, 28.21). **Limpopo:** Tuinplaas, Springbokflats (-24.9, 28.73); (NCA 2003/203); (NCA 2003/427) (NCA 2002/750); (NCA 2003/473); (NCA 2003/429); NCA 2003/886); (NCA 2003/829); (NCA 2003/476); (NCA 2003/474); (NCA 2003/475); (NCA 2003/828); Little Leigh, Western Soutpansberg (-22.94, 29.87) (NCA 2009/1702). **Mpumalanga:** Marble Hall (-24.96, 29.29) (NCA 2004/1215).

Figs 10–12. *Eleleis limpopo*: 8. Eye pattern. 9. Spinnerets. 10. Male palp (after Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020). 11. Female epigyne (after Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020). 12. Epigyne. (Photos: 8, 9, 12 Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman)

LIFESTYLE

Eleleis limpopo are free-running ground dwellers and they were sampled from the Grassland and Savanna Biomes. As part of the Gauteng Grassland Project (Webb & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014) the species was sampled annually since 2012 from grasslands around Pretoria, in Irene, and the Groenkloof Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lyle, 2014).

They are often found under rocks. They immediately move around to try to get under the rock again (Fig. 13). In Irene they were always associated with small red ants running between them. On the Springbok Flats a large number of specimens were sampled from pitfall traps over a period of a year (2001–2002). The males were sampled from September, October to November as well as in June and July. The females were sampled mainly in October. In Irene the species was photographed on 10 occasions – males mainly during June and July and females in April.

Fig. 13. *Eleleis limpopo* female collected from under rocks at Irene in grassland.

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Notes on the kidney garden spider *Bijoaraneus legonensis* (Grasshoff & Edmunds 1979) from South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

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ABSTRACT: Notes on the kidney garden spider *Bijoaraneus legonensis* (Grasshoff & Edmunds, 1979) are provided. The species is now known from Ghana, Thailand and South Africa. The general morphology, behaviour, conservation status and distribution of the species in South Africa are discussed, along with images of live specimens.

Keywords: biodiversity, conservation, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt Biome, KwaZulu-Natal, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSА), a large number of Araneidae genera were recorded over a period of 25 years (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). There were several species of *Araneus* Clerck, 1757, a genus unfortunately still poorly known in South Africa. *Araneus* is large spider genus, currently consisting of 543 species (World Spider Catalog, 2022). Over the years, many species have been moved from *Araneus* to other genera. In a phylogenetic study using five genes, Scharff *et al.* (2020) suggested that at least nine new genera should be established independently of *Araneus*.

During SANSА surveys, several specimens of the species *Araneus legonensis*, described by Grasshoff and Edmunds (1979) from Ghana, were identified. This species, known as the kidney garden spider, is easily recognisable from colour, abdominal patterns and web-building behaviour (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2007; Heron, 2017). It closely resembles *Araneus mitificus* (Simon, 1886), a species known from Cambodia. Tanikawa *et al.* (2021) examined both species and found that although they are very similar in general appearance, the shape of the epigyne and palps differs. They found that these species are different from *Araneus* and both were moved to a new genus, *Bijoaraneus* Tanikawa, Yamasaki & Petcharad, 2021. They identified specimens from Thailand as belonging to *B. legonensis* and the range of the species is presently Ghana and Thailand (World Spider Catalog, 2022).

The aim of this paper is to present additional information on *B. legonensis* in South Africa with notes of their morphology, behaviour, distribution and conservation status.

METHODS

During SANSА surveys, requests were made for photographs of species for the SANSА Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012) and several sets of photographs of *B. legonensis* were received from the public. Specimens collected during SANSА surveys were deposited as voucher specimens in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) of the Agricultural Research Council Plant Health and Protection division.

TAXONOMY

Bijoaraneus legonensis (Grasshoff & Edmunds, 1979)

Araneus legonensis Grasshoff & Edmunds, 1979: 303; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2007: 3; 2014: 44; Heron, 2017: 11–12.

Bijoaraneus legonensis, Tanikawa, Yamasaki & Petcharad, 2021: 99 (transfer from *Araneus*).

Figs 1–3. *Bijoaraneus legonensis* female: 1. Habitus lateral view. 2. Dorsal view. 3. Abdomen posterior view. (Photos: Peter Webb)

Figs 4–7. *Bijoaraneus legonensis* female: 4. Eye pattern. 5. Ventral view. 6. Epigyne after Tanikawa *et al.* (2021). 7. Epigyne after Grasshoff and Edmunds (1979). (Photos 4 & 5: Peter Webb)

Diagnostic characteristics: Female: Size total length 4–6 mm. Carapace pale brown in live specimens; lateral edges with a greenish tint (Figs 1 & 4); median eye region dark (Fig. 4); chelicerae with green tint; sternum pale brown to green (Fig. 5). Abdomen dorsal surface with white guanophores, decorated with black patterns (Figs 1–3) that vary between adults and juveniles; anterior edge dark fused with a crescent-shaped marking, sometimes only two fused black areas (amount of fusion varying between specimens); with four round dark abdominal maculae sometimes with yellow to green tint; lateral sides greenish; ventral surface bright green without guanophores with yellow tint in the booklung areas (Fig. 5). Legs chestnut brown with a dark annulation with some segments green. Male: Size: TL 3–4 mm. Resembles female.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Ghana, Thailand and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Eastern Cape: Katberg State Forest (-32.78, 26.62); East London (-33.01, 27.90). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Hilton (-29.56, 30.30); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Hell's Gate (-28.01, 32.48); Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); Tembe Elephant Park (-27.03, 32.42); Malvern, Queensburgh (-29.53, 30.55). **Limpopo:** Entabeni Forest (-23.00, 30.23); Luvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.04, 29.45); Legalameetse Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16); Soutpansberg, Farm Little Leigh (-22.94, 29.87); Woodbush (-23.78, 30.07). **Mpumalanga:** Nelshoogte Forest Reserve (-25.83, 30.83). **Western Cape:** Knysna Forest (-33.97, 23.02); Outeniqua Nature Reserve (-33.87, 22.48).

HABITAT

The species was sampled from the Fynbos, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Forest, Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011; Haddad *et al.*, 2013).

BEHAVIOUR

Web building: Grasshoff and Edmunds (1979) described the webs of *B. legonensis* from Ghana as having a free sector with a guideline connecting the hub to a resting silk retreat on a leaf nearby.

The hub is pulled towards the retreat by the guideline. The retreat consists of a silk sheet that pulls together the edges of a leaf (Figs 8–10). The spider rests on the under surface of the silk sheet (Fig. 11), usually with the tips of its first pair of legs just visible.

In KwaZulu-Natal, some webs of *B. legonensis* were observed by the second author (Heron, 2017). The first web was a small, near-vertical, incomplete yellow orb-web with a diameter of about 13 cm, approximately 1.5 m from the ground on the west-facing side of a tree that was shaded until mid-afternoon. A second web had a diameter of 14 cm. A wedge-shaped section of the upper portion of the web, facing a silken leaf retreat, was missing, and the central hub area was linked to the spider in its retreat by a silk thread. The silk retreat consisting of whitish threads had been constructed in an adjacent upward-folded leaf (Fig. 10). The enclosed spider could be easily observed inverted, hanging within the structure, and facing towards the orb-web. When disturbed, the spider quickly abandoned the structure and dropped to the ground with a silken line, where it remained immobile.

Figs 8–10. *Bijoaraneus legonensis* female in silk retreat made on leaves. (Photos: 8 & 9 Hugh Heron, 10. Peter Webb)

Figs 11–12. *Bijoaraneus legonensis* female: 11. In silk retreat made on leaves. 12. Abdomen showing the black spots. (Photos: 11. John Roff, 12. Peter Webb)

Fig. 13. Eyes of a Salticidae species.

Defense mechanism: Careful consideration was given to the posterior abdominal maculae (Heron, 2017). The photographers observed that when disturbed, the abdomen of the female was raised slightly to display the black spots. The purpose of the display was presumed to be defensive and it could be speculated that the spots were possibly serving two purposes: to draw attention away from the head by presenting a pattern reminiscent of eyes, and to possibly suggest the “face” of a predator. No predators of these spiders are known but from the size and arrangement, the pattern appeared reminiscent of the eyes of a salticid spider, with two large spots flanked by smaller ones, all with pale outlines. Although they were far larger than the eyes of any local salticid, this was possibly for a more startling effect, especially when viewed “face-on” (Figs 12 & 13).

CONSERVATION

Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of least concern. It is present in several protected areas such as the Legalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2016), Luvhondo Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2008), Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad *et al.*, 2010), Nelshoogte Forest Reserve and Outeniqua Nature Reserve.

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New records of *Oecobius putus* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876 from South Africa (Araneae: Oecobiidae)

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ABSTRACT: New records of the spider *Oecobius putus* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876 are provided from South Africa. The general morphology of live specimens is discussed and photographs are provided, with notes on their behaviour, distribution and conservation status.

Keywords: conservation, biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa)

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Oecobius* Lucas, 1846 is the largest genus of the Oecobiidae, known from 89 species and a single subspecies, and has a wide geographical range (World Spider Catalogue, 2022). Several species of *Oecobius* are synanthropic and widely distributed in the world. Cosmopolitan species known from the Afrotropical Region are *O. navus* Blackwall, *O. cellariorum* Duges and *O. putus* Pickard-Cambridge (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué, 1997).

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015), several *Oecobius* specimens were sampled but most of them belong to the cosmopolitan species *O. navus*, a species widely distributed throughout South Africa. Between the survey material, a second species, *O. putus*, described by O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876 from the Temple of Pbilse in Upper Egypt, was identified in 2010 (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010).

The general morphology of live specimens is discussed and photographs are provided, with notes on their behaviour, distribution and conservation status.

TAXONOMY

Oecobius putus O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876

Oecobius putus O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876: 544; Dippenaar-Schoeman 2010: 558; 2014: 106; 2021: 7.

Diagnostic characteristics: Size: total length female and male 2-3 mm, with males slightly smaller than females (Fig. 4). Carapace sub-circular, wider than long, without fovea; eight eyes arranged in two rows in compact group near centre of carapace, with posterior median eyes circular or oval (Figs 1–3); pale yellow with a brown band formed of irregular brown spots at the lateral margin; ocular area dark. Sternum heart-shaped, yellowish bordered with brown; furnished with scattered long black hairs; labium is wider than long, blackish in colour with a slightly rounded tip. Abdomen more or less flattened; oval to round; slightly overlapping carapace; variable darker cruciform marking and white subcutaneous pigment granules (Fig. 3) dense covering of white setae (Fig. 1). Leg colour similar to carapace. Palp shown in Figs 5 & 6 and epigyne in Figs 7 & 8.

Figs 1–3. *Oecobius putus*: 1. Female from Bloemfontein. 2. Female from Kuruman. 3. Male from Bloemfontein (Photos 1 & 3: Rudi Steenkamp, 2. Ruan Booyesen).

Figs 4–8. *Oecobius putus*: 4. Male and female from the Sandveld Nature Reserve (Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman). 5. Male palp (Charles Haddad). 6. Male palp after Kritscher (1966). 7. Epigyne (Charles Haddad). 8. Epigyne (Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman).

Figs 9–11. *Oecobius navus*: 9. Female from Irene (Peter Webb). 10. Epigyne. 11. Palp after Lawrence (1952).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Egypt, Sudan to Iran, Azerbaijan, Afghanistan, India. Introduced to USA, Mexico (World Spider Catalogue, 2022). New: South Africa.

KNOWN DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Free State: Sandveld Nature Reserve (-27.85, 25.93); Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22). **Northern Cape:** 39 km E of Groblers-hoop (-28.85, 22.30); Akkerendam Nature Reserve near Calvinia (-31.433, 19.783); Kuruman (-27.46, 23.43).

BEHAVIOUR

Oecobius species live in star-shaped mesh webs made over cracks, crevices and in the corners of rocks or walls. The web serves as a protective retreat while the anchor threads attached to the substrate notify the spider of approaching prey. The spider sits beneath the web on the substrate with its back facing the sheet. When prey touches a thread, the spider rushes out.

A video of *O. putus* taken by the second author shows how they rapidly circle the prey in an anti-clockwise, as well as clockwise, direction, enswathes it in silk using the stout, curved setae of the anal tubercle to comb the silk from the large posterior spinnerets, and then drags the prey under the disk web, after which it is discarded. When disturbed, the spider runs away rapidly from the retreat into a crevice nearby. *O. putus* were found in houses, where they often prey on ants, but also on small flies, bugs, and beetles.

Oecobius putus resembles *O. navus* in size and shape but the patterns on the body differ (Fig. 9), as well as the genitalia (Figs 10 & 11). The cephalic region of *O. putus* is lighter in colour (almost colourless), and the cardiac mark on the abdomen is dark brown to black. Conversely, the cephalic region of *O. navus* is clearly darkened, and the cardiac mark is light brown.

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Notes on the red ladybird beetle spider *Paraplectana thornntoni* (Blackwall, 1865) from South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

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Abstract: The genus *Paraplectana* Brito Capello, 1867 is known from Africa and Asia. *Paraplectana thornntoni* (Blackwall, 1865) is an African endemic species described by Blackwall (1865) from Mozambique and with their bright colours, they mimic beetle species belonging to the family Coccinellidae. A female *P. thornntoni* female was observed over a 10-day period on a farm in Barberton, Mpumalanga, South Africa. Observations on their behaviour, distribution and conservation are provided.

Keywords: behaviour, Cyrtarachninae, egg sac, spanning-web, velvet mites

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Paraplectana* is known from Africa and Asia. *Paraplectana thornntoni* (Blackwall, 1865) is an African endemic species described by Blackwall (1865) from Mozambique. They belong to the subfamily Cyrtarachninae. Members of this subfamily construct a “spanning thread-web”, a basic orb-web, but the web’s diameter, sticky spiral spacing and viscid thread diameter differ from that of typical orb-webs. The viscid threads are studded with large droplets. Each of the short threads between the radii is known as a spanning thread, and is unique in that it breaks when prey comes into contact with it. The prey flies into the web, gets stuck to a viscid thread, the thread breaks, and the spider pulls the prey up to the hub of the web to feed on (Stowe, 1986; Tanikawa *et al.*, 2014).

Paraplectana species are known as ladybird beetle spiders because they purportedly mimic beetles belonging to the family Coccinellidae and the tortoise beetles of the family Chrysomelidae (Heron, 2016). The beetles secrete a fluid from joints in their legs, which gives them a foul taste. This and their bright colours warn would-be attackers like birds to ignore them. For members of *Paraplectana*, with their vivid, aposematic colouration, it provides the necessary protection.

Two species have been recorded in South Africa and they can easily be recognised by their colour and abdominal patterns. The abdomen of *P. thornntoni* is shiny with a jet-black ground colour with raised, large and conspicuous bright orange-red, sometimes with markings dorsally (Figs 1a & 1b). This species is commonly known as the red ladybird beetle spider, while *P. walleri* (Blackwall, 1865) with its yellow body and black spots (Cooper & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2020) is known as yellow ladybird beetle spiders.

Paraplectana thornntoni is an African endemic species described by Blackwall (1865) as *Eurysoma thornntoni* from a region through which the Shire River flows to its confluence with the Zambesi in Mozambique. *Peniza testudo*, a junior synonym of *P. thornntoni*, was described by Thorell (1868) from Caffraria, an old name for parts of the Eastern Cape. It was also recorded by O. Pickard-Cambridge (1879) from Caffraria. In South Africa, although the species is rarely collected, it was sampled from four provinces (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022).

We present notes on the red ladybird beetle spider *P. thornntoni* from South Africa as observed by the first author (KdP) in the field. Images of a live specimen are provided with notes on web-building and egg-laying behaviour.

Fig. 1. *Paraplectana thornntoni* female: 1a. Dorsal view. 1b. Lateral view. (Photos: Kobie du Preez)

Fig. 2. *Paraplectana thornntoni* female with the ladybird beetles they mimic. (Photo: Susan Dippenaar)

Fig. 3a. *Paraplectana thorntoni* gravid female. 3b. A thinner female after egg laying. 3c. The egg sac. (Photos: Kobie du Preez)

METHODS

A female *P. thorntoni* was observed over a period of 12 days (13-25 April 2020) on Portion 8 of the farm Aylestone near Barberton in the Mpumalanga province by the first author (KdP). Photographs and videos were taken of the activities of the spiders (see BLOG <https://aylestone8.wordpress.com>). Unfortunately, the female disappeared before she could be sampled.

RESULTS

13 April 2020: A red ladybird beetle spider was discovered by the first author while walking through the bush on the farm Aylestone in Barberton, in the Lowveld of Mpumalanga, South Africa. This was early in the morning and photographs of the specimen were taken and it was identified as *P. thorntoni* of the family Araneidae (Figs 1a & 1b). The spider was not disturbed by any of the author's actions, and did not try to move away. It just sat on the leaf as if it was glued there. On the photographs (Fig. 1a), a small silk layer can be seen below the spider, which probably serves as a platform to cling to. From her swollen abdomen it could be deduced that she was most likely gravid.

14 April: The next morning, the spider was more or less in the same spot as the day before, in the open, not hiding and stuck to her post with her legs neatly tucked in as the day before. This was her daytime posture that I observed in the next week or so.

15 April: Even after a 42 mm rain shower the night before, she was still in the same position on the bush. She remained on the same bush for a few more days.

19 April: In the morning and afternoon, she was gone.

20 April: In the morning an egg sac was found in the grass, approximately 30 cm from the ground (Fig. 3c). However, the female was still missing. The egg sac was secured to the grass with silk and looked quite sturdy. The whole structure was 40 mm in length and 12 mm in width. Only in the late afternoon was the female eventually found in her new hiding spot in a thorn tree close to the egg sac. She was visibly flatter than before (Fig. 3b).

Fig. 4. *Paraplectana thorntoni*: 4a. Female moving around building the web. 4b. Web after egg laying. 4c. Web a few days later. 4d. Egg sac with red velvet mite. (Photos: Kobie du Preez)

That night, her web was only two strands of silk without diagonal reinforcements (Fig. 4b). A loose strand with a large drop of the sticky fluid was swaying loose. Her energy was clearly used on building her egg sac. While constructing the web, it was very interesting to see her pulling threads with sticky droplets from her spinnerets (Fig. 4a). A video of the process was taken and it can be viewed at <https://youtu.be/1PRfnU6sRLA>.

21 April: The spider was breaking down the web early in the morning. She was reeling in the silk strands and gathered them in a bundle close to her cephalothorax. A video of the process can be viewed at <https://youtu.be/NciP7aRy3og>.

22 April: The spider was not found in the morning or during the day. The egg sac remained unchanged. That night she was found about one metre to the back. Two main strands of silk were used and she was busy eating. At least her hard work was paying off in a nice meal.

23 April: Day 10 since she was discovered, her condition improved again and her egg sac was still intact. That night, her web was a bit more intricate than the previous night, so she definitely had more energy. The silk strands were now diagonal again. A moth (still alive) was dangling from a loose strand.

24 April: In the photo taken that morning, one can visibly see the difference in her condition; her abdomen was inflated again.

27 April: Unfortunately, at this stage, the female had disappeared. On the egg sac a larger red arachnid was visible (Fig. 4d) and it was now becoming clear that they definitely were not spiderlings but red velvet mites that invaded the egg sac (Fig. 5a).

5 May: The egg sac was opened and 22 mites of different sizes were found. Some were too large to fit through the tiny holes and they must have cannibalised the other mites to survive.

CONCLUSION

Little is still known about the behaviour of many spiders in South Africa, especially species of rare genera such as *Paraplectana*. We now know they sit on top of leaves during the day. They build their webs at night, which is a spanning thread-web. They feed on moths and they are found in low vegetation and possibly mimic the ladybird beetle that is also an inhabitant of low vegetation. Their egg sac is attached to the vegetation and could thus be parasitised by red velvet mites.

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Fig. 5. *Paraplectana thornstoni* egg sac infested with red velvet mites (Photo: Kobie du Preez)

Gauteng Urban Surveys 1. Checklist of the spiders of the Faerie Glen Nature Reserve in Pretoria, South Africa (Arachnida, Araneae)

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ABSTRACT: Little is known about the diversity of invertebrates in urban areas in South Africa. This survey of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) forms part of the Spider Monitoring in Cities (SMC) project of SANSa. The results of sampling undertaken over a six-year period in Faerie Glen Nature Reserve in the Gauteng province, South Africa, is provided. A total of 103 species, 85 genera, from 31 families were recorded. Sampling was mainly done by sweeping and hand collecting. The most species-rich families were the Salticidae (17 spp.), Araneidae (12 spp.), followed by the Thomisidae (11 spp.), while 19 families are represented by singletons. The conservation status and level of endemism based on their known distribution are provided for each species. Four of the species are vulnerable and one is near threatened.

Keywords: conservation, endemism, diversity, South African National Survey of Arachnida, urban surveys

INTRODUCTION

This survey forms part of the Spider Monitoring in Cities (SMC) project of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa). The project was initiated in 2014 (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lyle, 2014). The green urban areas can be potential corridors for dispersal of wildlife through urban areas, promoting connectivity between species' meta-populations both within and outside towns and cities. Unfortunately, the evidence for these functions for spiders in Southern Africa is either anecdotal or completely lacking. The first report on spiders in urban areas was by Tucker (1920) on the spiders of Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden, while Clark and Samways (1997) studied arthropods, including spiders, in a botanic garden in Pietermaritzburg, South Africa. More recently, surveys were undertaken in the Free State National Botanical Garden Bloemfontein, South Africa (Butler & Haddad 2011; Neethling & Haddad, 2013, 2018).

Gauteng is by far the smallest province, covering only 1.4% of South Africa. As part of SANSa, a total of 350 sites in Gauteng have already been sampled, represented by 6 800 records, 56 families and 641 species (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). This includes a total of 24 protected areas. Surveys in Gauteng urban areas include several reserves and botanical gardens: Serene Valley (Kelly *et al.*, 2014), Tswaing Crater Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014), Groenkloof Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lyle, 2014), as well as the Pretoria National Botanical Gardens (Kassimatis, 2008), Rietondale Research Station (Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1991) and Irene grassland survey. Other surveys not in urban areas include surveys in agro ecosystems at the Agricultural Research Council (ARC) Roodeplaat Campus (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1976) and Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1989; Engelbrecht, 2013).

This paper presents the first species list and information on the spider fauna of the Faerie Glen Nature Reserve. Information on endemism and conservation status for each of the 102 species is provided.

METHOD

Study area: The Faerie Glen Nature Reserve (25° 46' 16.2516" S; 28° 17' 40.47" E) in Pretoria forms part of the Bronberg Conservation Area, which was declared in 1980. It is a 128-ha area in urban surroundings, boasting idyllic scenery, an abundance of birdlife and a series of nature trails and walks. The reserve transitions between *bankenveld* (grassland) and sour bushveld (acacia veld). The reserve also forms part of the 8-km Moreleta Spruit Nature Trail, while the perennial Moreleta Spruit flows through it, which is responsible for abundant grassland and rich vegetation.

Sampling methods and identification: The second author (PW) hand collected specimens, as well as using a sweepnet. He visited the reserve in 2013 (June), 2014 (February, April, September), 2015 (April), 2017 (November) and 2020 (February). Live spiders were sampled, photographed and then preserved in 70% ethanol. Identifications were done in Pretoria by the first author (ASD) and the voucher specimens are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the ARC-Plant Health and Protection division in Pretoria. Some of the species could not be identified to species level because only immature specimens were sampled or the taxonomy of some families is still unresolved (Tables 1 & 3).

Endemicity value: The endemicity value for each species is provided (Table 3) based on its currently known distribution. Seven endemicity categories are recognised: 6 = when Faerie Glen Nature Reserve is the type locality; 5 = GE, endemic to the Gauteng province but wider than the type locality; 4 = SAE endemic to South Africa but known from two adjoining provinces; 3 = SAE South African endemic, known from more than two provinces or two provinces not adjoining; 2 = STHE, endemic to Southern Africa (south of Zambezi and Kunene Rivers); 1 = AE, known from the Afrotropical Region (African Endemic); 0 = cosmopolitan, Africa and wider (C).

Conservation status: As part of the Red Listing Spider Project (Foord *et al.*, 2020), the preliminary conservation status of species was determined. Immatures, new species and undetermined taxa were not evaluated (NE). Species known from only one sex, or where only very old material is available, or species that could not be identified were listed as DDT (data deficient for taxonomic reasons) or DD when there is a lack of distribution data. Species with a broad distribution (categories 0–2) were considered to be of least concern (LC); those of categories 3 and 4 were considered to be South African endemics (SAE), and many of them are also LC; while species of special concern usually belong to categories 5 or 6.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numbers present: In total, 103 species in 85 genera and 31 families were sampled (Tables 1 & 3). Four species (Araneidae, Theridiidae, Mimetidae and Oxyopidae) could not be identified to species level as they were probably new or still immature. Unfortunately, some of them belong to large families that require comprehensive revision to determine the taxonomic status and identity of these taxa.

Family diversity: Of the 31 spider families collected from Faerie Glen Nature Reserve (Tables 1 & 2), the Salticidae (17 spp.), Araneidae (12 spp.) and Thomisidae with (11 spp.) were the most species-rich.

Endemicity: Forty-eight species (46.6%) sampled at Faerie Glen Nature Reserve have a wide distribution throughout Africa (AE) while 17.5% are known from Southern Africa and only 23.2% are South African endemics.

Four species are Gauteng endemics: *Hortipes coccinatus* Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000 (Corinnidae); *Idiops pretoriae* (Pocock, 1898) (Idiopidae) and two members of the Stasimopidae: *Stasimopus hewitti* Engelbrecht and Prendini, 2012 and *S. robertsi* Hewitt, 1910.

TABLE 1: Spider diversity of Faerie Glen Nature Reserve with the total number of families, genera (G) and species (SPP.)

FAMILIES	G	SPP.	FAMILIES	G	SPP.
Amaurobiidae	1	1	Oxyopidae	1	6
Araneidae	10	12	Palpimanidae	1	1
Bemmeridae	1	1	Philodromidae	3	3
Cheiracanthiidae	1	1	Pholcidae	1	1
Clubionidae	1	1	Phyxelididae	1	1
Corinnidae	2	2	Pisauridae	3	3
Cyrtacheniidae	1	1	Salticidae	14	17
Deinopidae	1	1	Scytodidae	1	1
Eresidae	1	1	Segestriidae	1	1
Gnaphosidae	6	7	Selenopidae	1	1
Hersiliidae	1	1	Stasimopidae	1	2
Idiopidae	3	3	Theridiidae	7	9
Linyphiidae	1	1	Thomisidae	8	11
Lycosidae	5	6	Trachelidae	2	2
Mimetidae	1	1	Uloboridae	2	2
Oecobiidae	1	1		85	103

TABLE 2: Conservation status and endemicity of the spider species sampled at Faerie Glenn Nature Reserve

Conservation status	No. of spp.	Code	%
Data deficient (taxonomic reason or lack distribution data)	0	DD	0
Not evaluated (immature, new or undetermined)	4	NE	3.9
Least concern	94	LC	91.3
Vulnerable	4	VU	3.9
Near threatened	1	NT	0.9
Endemicity			
0 – Africa and wider (C)	9	LC	8.7
1 – African endemics (AE)	48	LC	46.6
2 – Southern African endemics (STHE)	18	LC	17.5
3 – South African endemics (SAE): More than three provinces	19	LC	18.4
4 – South African endemics (SAE): Two adjacent provinces	1	VU	0.9
5 – Gauteng endemics (GE)	4	VU,NT	3.9
6 – Type locality	0		0

Stasimopus robertsi Photo Les Oates

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Figs 1–15. Spiders collected at the Faerie Glen Nature Reserve: 1. *Araneus apricus* (Araneidae). 2. *Neoscona subfusca* (Araneidae). 3. *Pararaneus cyrtoscapus* (Araneidae). 4. *Lipocrea longissima* (Araneidae). 5. *Hyposisinga holzapfelae* (Araneidae). 6. *Menneus camelus* (Deinopidae). 7. *Micaria beaufortia* (Gnaphosidae). 8. *Merenius alberti* (Corinnidae). 9. *Hortipes coccinatus* (Corinnidae). 10. *Cheiracanthium furculatum* (Cheiracanthiidae). 11. *Camillina cordifera* (Gnaphosidae). 12. *Pardosa crassipalpis* (Lycosidae). 13. *Hogna zuluana* (Lycosidae). 14. *Oxyopes bothai* (Oxyopidae). 15. *Oxyopes* sp. 3.

Photo credit: Peter Webb

Figs 16-29. Spiders collected at the Faerie Glen Nature Reserve: 16. *Vidole sothoana* (Phyxelididae). 17. *Heliophanus debilis* (Salticidae). 18. *Pellenes bulawayoensis* (Salticidae). 19. *Pseudicius gracilis* (Salticidae). 20. *Natta horizontalis* (Salticidae). 21. *Afrocto martini* (Trachelidae). 22. *Enoplognatha molesta* (Theridiidae). 23. *Steatoda capensis* (Theridiidae). 24. *Ariadna bilineata* (Segestriidae). 25. *Scytodes elizabethae* (Scytodidae). 26. *Rothus aethiopicus* (Pisauridae). 27. *Miagrammopes brevicaudus* (Uloboridae). 28. *Synema imitatrix* (Thomisidae). 29. *Thomisus blandus* (Thomisidae). 30. *Runcinia aethiops* (Thomisidae). Photo credit: Peter Webb

TABLE 1: Spiders of the Faerie Glen Nature Reserve, listing their endemism (END), conservation status (CS), global distribution and known sex F (female), M (male), B (both).

FAMILY, SPECIES	END	CS	DIST	SEX
FAMILY AMAUROBIIDAE				
<i>Chresiona invalida</i> (Simon, 1898)	3	LC	SAE	F
FAMILY ARANEIDAE				
<i>Araneus apricus</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE	F
<i>Argiope australis</i> (Walckenaer, 1805)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Cyphalonotus larvatus</i> (Simon, 1881)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Hypsosinga holzapfelae</i> (Lessert, 1936)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Hypsosinga lithyphantoides</i> Caporiacco, 1947	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Lipocrea longissima</i> (Simon, 1881)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Neoscona blondeli</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Pararaneus cyrtoscapus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Prasonica seriata</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Zygiella</i> sp.		NE		
FAMILY BEMMERIDAE				
<i>Homostola vulpecula</i> Simon, 1892	3	LC	SAE	F
FAMILY CHEIRACANTHIIDAE				
<i>Cheiracanthium furculatum</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE	B
FAMILY CLUBIONIDAE				
<i>Clubiona africana</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE	B
FAMILY CORINNIDAE				
<i>Hortipes coccinatus</i> Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000	5	VU	SAE	B
<i>Merenius alberti</i> Lessert, 1923	2	LC	STHE	B
FAMILY CYRTAUCHENIIDAE				
<i>Ancylotrypa pretoriae</i> (Hewitt, 1913)	3	LC	SAE	B
FAMILY DEINOPIIDAE				
<i>Menneus camelus</i> Pocock, 1902	3	LC	SAE	B
FAMILY ERESIDAE				
<i>Dresserus colsoni</i> Tucker, 1920	3	LC	SAE	F
FAMILY GNAPHOSIDAE				
<i>Camillina cordifera</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Drassodes splendens</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Micaria beaufortia</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Micaria felix</i> Booysen & Haddad, 2021	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Setaphis subtilis</i> (Simon, 1897)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Xerophaeus vickermani</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Zelotes corrugatus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE	B
FAMILY HERSILIIDAE				
<i>Hersilia sericea</i> Pocock, 1898	1	LC	AE	B
FAMILY IDIOPIDAE				
<i>Galeosoma robertsi</i> Hewitt, 1916	4	VU	SAE	F
<i>Idiops pretoriae</i> (Pocock, 1898)	5	VU	SAE	B
<i>Segregara transvaalensis</i> (Hewitt, 1913)	3	LC	SAE	B

FAMILY LINYPHIIDAE

<i>Microlinyphia sterilis</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	0	LC	C	B
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FAMILY LYCOSIDAE

<i>Allocosa tuberculipalpa</i> (Caporiacco, 1940)	1	LC	AE	B
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<i>Hogna lawrencei</i> (Roewer, 1960)	3	LC	SAE	F
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<i>Hogna zuluana</i> Roewer, 1959	3	LC	SAE	F
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<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE	B
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<i>Proevippa albiventris</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE	B
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<i>Trabea purcelli</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE	B
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FAMILY MIMETIDAE

<i>Mimetus</i> sp.			NE	
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FAMILY OECOBIIDAE

<i>Oecobius navus</i> Blackwall, 1859	0	LC	C	B
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FAMILY OXYOPIDAE

<i>Oxyopes affinis</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE	B
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<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE	F
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<i>Oxyopes</i> sp. 3			NE	
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<i>Oxyopes hoggi</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE	B
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<i>Oxyopes longispinosus</i> Lawrence, 1938	3	LC	SAE	B
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<i>Oxyopes vogelsangeri</i> Lessert, 1946	1	LC	AE	B
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FAMILY PALPIMANIDAE

<i>Palpimanus transvaalicus</i> Simon, 1893	3	LC	SAE	F
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FAMILY PHILODROMIDAE

<i>Gephyrota glauca</i> (Jézéquel, 1966)	1	LC	AE	B
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<i>Philodromus brachycephalus</i> Lawrence, 1952	1	LC	AE	F
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<i>Tibellus minor</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE	B
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FAMILY PHOLCIDAE

<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	2	LC	STHE	B
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FAMILY PHYXELIDIDAE

<i>Vidole sothoana</i> Griswold, 1990	2	LC	STHE	B
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FAMILY PISAUROIDAE

<i>Chiasmopes lineatus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE	B
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<i>Euprosthénopsis vuattouxi</i> Blandin, 1977	1	LC	AE	B
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<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE	B
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FAMILY SALTICIDAE

<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE	B
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<i>Cyrba nigrimana</i> Simon, 1900	3	LC	SAE	B
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<i>Evarcha prosimilis</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	1	LC	AE	B
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<i>Festucula leroyae</i> Azarkina & Foord, 2014	2	LC	STHE	B
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<i>Heliophanus aberdarensis</i> Wesolowska, 1986	1	LC	AE	B
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<i>Heliophanus debilis</i> Simon, 1901	1	LC	AE	B
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<i>Heliophanus lesserti</i> Wesolowska, 1986	1	LC	AE	B
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<i>Heliophanus nanus</i> Wesolowska, 2003	2	LC	STHE	B
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FAMILY SALTICIDAE

<i>Icius insolidus</i> (Wesołowska, 1999)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Menemerus transvaalicus</i> Wesołowska, 1999	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Myrmarachne inflatipalpis</i> Wanless, 1978	1	LC	AE	M
<i>Natta horizontalis</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Pellenes bulawayoensis</i> Wesołowska, 2000	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Pignus simoni</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Pseudicius gracilis</i> Haddad & Wesołowska, 2011	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Thyene thyenioides</i> (Lessert, 1925)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Tusitala barbata</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	1	LC	AE	B

FAMILY SCYTODIDAE

<i>Scytodes elizabethae</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE	M
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FAMILY SEGESTRIIDAE

<i>Ariadna bilineata</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE	F
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FAMILY SELENOPIDAE

<i>Anyphops barbertonensis</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	1	LC	AE	F
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FAMILY STASIMOPIDAE

<i>Stasimopus hewitti</i> Engelbrecht & Prendini, 2012	5	VU	SAE	B
<i>Stasimopus robertsi</i> Hewitt, 1910	5	NT	SAE	B

FAMILY THERIDIIDAE

<i>Enoplognatha molesta</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Episinus marignaci</i> (Lessert, 1933)	2	LC	STHE	F
<i>Euryopis episinoides</i> (Walckenaer, 1847)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C	B
<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C	B
<i>Theridion piliphilum</i> Strand, 1907	3	LC	SAE	F
<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Theridion</i> sp. 2		NE		
<i>Tidarren scenicum</i> (Thorell, 1899)	1	LC	AE	F

FAMILY THOMISIDAE

<i>Diaea puncta</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Oxytate argenteooculata</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Runcinia aethiops</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Synema imitatrix</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Thomisops bullatus</i> Simon, 1895	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Thomisus blandus</i> Karsch, 1880	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Thomisus daradioides</i> Simon, 1890	0	LC	C	B
<i>Thomisus kalaharinus</i> Lawrence, 1936	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock, 1900	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Xysticus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1938	2	LC	STHE	B

FAMILY TRACHELIDAE

<i>Afroceto martini</i> (Simon, 1897)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Orthobula radiata</i> Simon, 1897	1	LC	AE	B

FAMILY ULOBORIDAE

<i>Miagrammopes brevicaudus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1882	2	LC	STHE	F
<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846	0	LC	C	B

Endemicity (END): (6) Only known from the type locality, Faerie Glen Nature Reserve endemic; (5) endemic to Gauteng province; (4) known from two adjoining provinces; (3) endemic to South Africa; (2) endemic to Southern Africa; (1) endemic to the Afrotropical Region; (0) also recorded outside the Afrotropical Region.

Conservation status (CS): LC, least concern; DD, data deficient; NE, not evaluated; VU, vulnerable.

Distribution (DIS): C, cosmopolitan or wider than Africa; AE, African endemic; STHE, Southern African endemic; SAE, South African endemic; GE, Gauteng endemic.